

Parents' Involvement in Students' Learning

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14187845

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Abstract:

This study determined the level of parents' involvement in students' learning in one of the middle schools in Beijing, China, during the school year 2022-2023. The study's respondents are 50 parents using descriptive research design utilizing the frequency count, simple percentage, weighted mean, and Mann-Whitney U-Test to interpret the data collected. The level of parents' involvement in students' learning was determined according to the areas; Parenting, Communicating, Decision-making and Collaborating with the community. Findings revealed that the level of parental involvement in students' learning in the area of Decision-making was high and in the area of collaborating with the community was moderate. Meanwhile, the level of parental involvement in the students learning in the area of parenting, communicating, decision-making, and collaborating with the community was the same. Based on the findings, this study calls for teachers to create programs that will generate parent-teacher partnership, recognition of parents and child's achievement in school aside from giving report cards. Also, School heads and teachers should build a comfortable learning environment to sustain the learners' interest and open communication with the parents, and conduct regular consultations and orientation of the school vision and mission for the welfare of their children. Further, parents should be informed through letters or an info board with a schedule within the allotted time. And lastly, teachers and school heads create a grouping for parents to collaborate on school projects with the goal of their children's welfare in school.

Keywords: Parents' Involvement, students' learning

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Parents' involvement is not something done to children. Still, it is a way of observing parents as active collaborators in students' learning and development of educational activities based on schools and supported by families that play a crucial role in children's growth. According to Tafesse (2015), parents are the first decisive individuals who need to play their part regarding students' learning responsibly. Parental involvement in their children's education enhances a child's motivation, outlook, and academic performance in all subject areas and encourages improved conduct and social development. In all these ways, family attachment in education helps children become productive and responsible members of society.

When schools, families, and community groups, in general, work together to support learning, children tend to do better and stay in school longer. Numerous studies have shown that adolescents with active parents are more likely to succeed academically, perform well on standardized tests, enlist in more advanced programs, pass their courses, and gain credits, regardless of their family's financial situation or history. The research shows that the relationship between parents' involvement and the improvement of their children's academic performance is not an absolute causal relationship but a close correlation, which is affected by various factors such as their social class and cultural environment.

Factors such as parents' educational level, occupational status, and family economy will affect the growth of teenagers. It has been found that parents' involvement is characterized by class differences due to economic, cultural, and social capital differences. Some researchers have tracked this impact and found that families impact students' academic performance through family resources and parental involvement. Family socio-economic status is one factor that affects children's academic performance, and children's development is also affected by other factors. In this sense, those "disadvantaged families" hindered by economic and other factors must try to break the barriers from external conditions to obtain high-quality and balanced education.

In addition, according to the relevant research on family education, parents' involvement may also impact children's psychological and behavioral problems beyond learning. Therefore, as a parent, the researcher is personally motivated to conduct this study to know the level of parents' involvement in the students learning and that this study needs to be further explored and studied.

Current State of Knowledge

To understand parents' concerns and create support for the reopening plans, it will be crucial to communicate with school communities often and in a clear and timely manner. What safety measures have been implemented to reduce health hazards will interest parents. They must also know the institution's adherence to fundamental educational tenets and objectives. Teachers must be ready to guarantee that everyone is informed because they are frequently parents' initial point of contact (UNESCO, 2020). On the other hand, a previous article by Machebe et al. (2017) viewed that parents who are worried about money and employment, working unsocial hours in more than one job, are likely to have less time to provide for their children with an environment conducive to good educational outcomes.

Parental involvement at home can include discussions about school, helping with learning activities, and formative assessment (Sheldon, 2018). Conversely, Cotton and Wiklund (2019) said there are compelling arguments in favor of parent participation models, including parents collaborating closely with their kids on learning activities at home. Programs that encourage parents to read to their children, assist them with schoolwork, or tutor them using materials and guidelines supplied by instructors have excellent outcomes. Spinelli and colleagues' (2020) study, "Parenting Stress during the COVID-19 Outbreak: Socioeconomic and Environmental Risk Factors and Implications for Children Emotion Regulation," showed that more stressed parents were less involved in their children's learning activities during the pandemic.

In order to make a practical parent-school relationship for enhancing the child's academic performance, his paper has suggested some strategies for Garbe et al. (2020), studied "COVID-19 and Remote Learning: Experiences of Parents with Children during the Pandemic," which opined those parents were unprepared for this shift since the pandemic was so sudden and unsuspected. They need help to balance their work, home, and teaching responsibilities. Their workplaces needed to prepare better. Parents were attempting to work remotely or unable to work while caring for children and trying to help them with their education, with no clarity on how long this closure would last. The study's results suggest essential implications and recommendations for educators and policymakers.

On the one hand, the parents are highly engaged in giving praise every time their child finishes answering assigned activities in their module. This underscores the notion that parents use positive verbal reinforcement, such as praises, to describe their child's positive behavior, express admiration, and their parental warmth (Gumapac et al. 2021, "Parents Involvement in Accomplishing Students Learning Tasks in the New Normal). The study recommends distributing the guide to intensify and strengthen parents' engagement in modular distance learning, increasing parental involvement.

Studies have been conducted on the impact of family education investment and parents' education background on the academic performance of junior high school students. Through multiple regression analysis, it is concluded that family education investment and parents' education background significantly positively impact academic performance. In addition, this paper also explored the mediating role of family educational investment and parental educational background on academic performance and found that family educational investment plays a mediating role between parental educational background and academic performance (Xiong et al., 2019).

Another study on the relationship between family education participation, social support, and student achievement by conducting a questionnaire survey on 502 students and their parents. The results showed that parental participation in students' learning and family education support has a significant positive correlation with students' academic performance, and social support also had a significant positive correlation with students' academic performance. At the same time, parent's educational background and socio-economic status also impacted students' academic performance (Maguate & Rabacal, 2023). Therefore, family education participation and social support can be used as one of the essential ways to improve students' academic performance (Li et al., 2020).

Based on the empirical data of students in higher vocational colleges in Shandong Province, this study explored the relationship between parental involvement in student learning and academic performance. The research showed that parents' participation behavior significantly impacts students' academic performance. Parents' participation in learning can promote students' interests and attitudes and improve learning effects. From the perspective of students in higher vocational colleges, this study explored the relationship between parental participation in student learning and academic performance. The research results showed that parents' participation in students' learning could promote students' learning interests and learning attitudes and improve the learning effect. The study also emphasized the positive impact of parental participation on students' academic performance, providing a theoretical basis for parents'

Theoretical Underpinnings

The Parental Involvement Theory by Joyce Epstein (1989) is the foundation for this investigation. According to the hypothesis, children whose parents are interested in their schooling are likelier than those whose parents are uninvolved to acquire a robust and beneficial sense of efficacy for accomplishing school-related activities.

The six categories of parental involvement—parenting, communicating, volunteering, at-home learning, decision-making, and collaboration—implied that parents who are involved and educated about their kids' education can positively affect their attitude and performance. This theory applies to the present study because it accounts for the extent of parents' involvement in students learning.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the level of parents' involvement in students' learning in one of the middle schools in Beijing, China, during the school year 2022-2023. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: 1) What is the profile of the respondents in terms of age, highest educational attainment and average family monthly income; 2) what is the level of parents' involvement in students' learning according to the area of parenting, communicating, decision-making and collaborating with the community; and 3) the significant difference in the level of parents' involvement in students' learning when grouped and compared according to the abovementioned variables.

Methodology:

This section presents the discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedure for data analysis.

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive research design, which fits this study as it seeks to determine the extent of parents' involvement in students learning in one of the primary schools in China during the school year 2022-2023. Silverio (2019) states that the Descriptive Research Design of research illustrates present characteristics, conditions, images, and the like based on the respondents' impressions, perceptions, or reactions.

This research design is appropriate for determining the parents' involvement in students learning. This research design fits the purpose of the present study as it entails observation, analysis, and mainly a description of factors. Survey questionnaires also qualify this study as a descriptive research design.

Study Respondents

The study's respondents are the parents in the middle school in one of the province schools in Beijing, China, during the school year 2022-2023, from a total population of 50. Since the number of respondents is small, the purposive random sampling technique was used. To get the percentage, the respondents from each section were divided by the total number of respondents and multiplied by the sample size.

Instruments

This study utilized a self-made questionnaire. The researcher-made questionnaire was divided into two parts. The first part comprised the personal profile of the respondents in terms of age, highest educational attainment, average family monthly income, and the number of children. The second part was the questionnaire proper, which included the parents' involvement in students learning with 30-line-item questions according to the following types: parenting, communicating, volunteering, learning at home, decision-making, and collaborating with a five-line item per type. This study utilized the Likert scale rating of five (5) as always, four (4) as often, three (3) as sometimes,

two (2) as rarely, and one (1) as almost never. The research instrument was subjected to validity (4.60-excellent) and reliability (0.896-good). All of them were interpreted as worthy and good; respectively.

Data Gathering Procedure

In gathering all the data needed for this research, the first step was to validate the research questionnaire. Three (3) experts from the field were tapped to validate the questions. Afterward, the researcher secured a permission letter from the School Principal. Upon approval, the said letter request was distributed to the School Head or teachers. After confirming the support for the second request, questionnaires were administered to the section advisers of each section. With the help of the section advisers, the researcher distributed and administered the questionnaires to the target respondents during the distribution and retrieval of questionnaires, observing the safety health protocols such as wearing a mask, face shields, and social distancing. This can be done using test questionnaires.

All data gathered in this study were treated with the utmost confidentiality. Upon retrieval of the survey questionnaire, the data collected were sent to the statistician for the tabulation, application of the appropriate statistical tools in every problem, analysis, and present the data in a tabular manner.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 used descriptive and analytical schemes and frequency count, and percentage to determine to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of age, highest educational attainment, and average family monthly income.

Objective No. 2 used descriptive and analytical schemes and mean to determine the level of parents’ involvement in students learning according to the following areas: parenting, communicating, decision-making, and collaborating.

Objective No.3 utilized a comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test to determine the significant difference in the level of parents’ involvement in the students learning when grouped and compared according to the abovementioned variables.

Ethical Consideration

This study strictly adhered to the research ethics protocol. The researcher secured the necessary permits before gathering the data. He also explained the purpose of administering the survey to the parents as respondents. More so, the researcher ensured the participants’ safety and consent to participate in this study. The researcher explains the respondents’ right to withdraw from the study for a valid reason. The researcher also gave instructions for completing the survey, answering questions, and clarifying the respondents’ doubts and confusions. Furthermore, the researcher handled the data with the highest anonymity and confidentiality level.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Table 2
Profile of Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Younger (below 41 years old)	27	54.00
	Older(41 years old and above)	23	46.00
	Total	50	100
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower (High School)	36	72.00
	Higher (Bachelors and Masters Degree)	14	28.00
	Total	50	100
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower (Less than 23 000 RMB)	30	60.00
	Higher (23 000 RMB and above)	20	40.00
	Total	50	100

As presented in Table 2, 27, or 54.00% of the respondents, are younger or below 41 years old, while 23, or 46.00%, are older or 41 years old and above. For the highest educational attainment, 36 or 72.00% of the respondents are high school graduates, while 14 or 28.00% are Bachelor's and Master's degree graduates. For variable average family monthly income, 30 or 60.00% of the respondents belonged to a family with an average monthly payment below RMB 23,000.00. In comparison, 20 or 40.00% of the respondents belonged to a family with an average monthly income of RMB 23,000.00 and above.

It implies that the younger parents contributed a more significant number of respondents. Many of the parents have lower educational attainment, and many have a lower average family monthly income. It is also said that older parents with higher educational backgrounds would have better knowledge and understanding of involvement in developing their children's learning. The results contrast with the study conducted by Bajande (2021) on parents' difficulties, wherein the researcher found out that most of the research participants are older parents, many of whom have higher educational attainment, and many have higher incomes.

Table 3
Level of parents' involvement in students learning in the area of Parenting

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a parent ...		
1. I fulfill my child's basic needs like food clothing and shelter.	4.62	Very High Level
2. I make sure that my child's attends school in compliance with all the rules and regulation.	4.60	Very High Level
3. I discuss the importance of good education with my child.	4.04	High Level
4. I monitor my child's progress and weaknesses in every grading period.	4.54	Very High Level
5. I supervise my child homework and projects.	4.60	Very High Level
6. I participate in learning activities with my child, such as playing educative games at home.	4.04	High Level
7. I help my child to prepare reviewers for her/his test and examination.	3.78	High Level
Overall Mean	4.32	High Level

Table 3 presents the level of parental involvement in students' learning in the area of Parenting. The respondents obtained an overall mean score of 4.32, which is a high level. This shows that most parents do their involvement in parenting very well toward students learning.

However, to go deeper in the analysis, respondents assessed a highest mean score of 4.62 on item No.1, which states, ". I fulfill my child's basic needs like food clothing and shelter" and is interpreted as "very high level." On the other hand, the lowest mean of 3.78 was on item No. 7, which states, "I help my child to prepare reviewers for her/his test and examination" and is interpreted as "high level."

This implies that most parents need more time to make or prepare reviewers for their examination and test. Some parents are exhausted after doing household chores or office work. Hence, less time was allotted to their children. At the same time, some parents work during the day, so they need more time to prepare their reviewers. With a busy timetable, parents need more time to review their children's lessons as much as they would like.

The findings were supported by Bhamani et al. (2020), wherein the researchers disclosed that parents with job issues could be extremely challenging as they can hardly sort out a time to read with their children and give frequent guidance.

Moreover, parental involvement at home can include discussions about school, helping with learning activities, and formative assessment (Sheldon, 2018). On the other hand, Cotton and Wiklund's (2019) article stated that there are strong indications that the most effective forms of parent involvement are those which engage parents in working directly with their children on learning activities in the home.

Table 4

Level of parents' involvement in students learning according to the area of Communicating

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a parent ...		
1. I meet my child's teacher at school during report card day.	3.16	Moderate Level
2. I read the school newsletters.	4.40	High Level
3. I take the initiative in contacting my child's teacher.	4.08	High Level
4. If I have any questions pertaining to my child, I can contact my child's teacher.	4.00	High Level
5. I receive information regarding my child's educational/ academic progress from his/her teacher and/or school.	3.48	Moderate Level
6. I can talk to the teacher about his/her activities and what was learned in school.	3.28	Moderate Level
7. I can talk to the teacher about my child's schedule of activities in school.	3.24	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.66	High Level

Table 4 discloses the results on the level of parental involvement in students' communication learning. Respondents assessed an overall mean score of 3.66 and interpreted it as high. This shows that most parents communicated well with school authorities concerning their students' learning. However, for further investigation of the results, the respondents perceived a highest mean score of 4.40 on item No. 2, which states, "I read the school newsletters," and interpreted as "high level," while the lowest mean of 3.16 was on item No. 1 which states " I meet my child's teacher at school during report card day" and interpreted as "moderate level."

This implies that most parents rarely attend school conferences, specifically while giving report cards, because they sometimes feel that they are not welcome in schools aside from being preoccupied with many household chores and job demands. This conforms to a previous article of Lemmer's, 2007 as cited by Ntekane (2018) showed that the reason for parents not to be involved in school is the fact that schools sometimes fail to create strong links between homes and schools or an environment where parents do not feel welcomed in schools more especially low-income earners. This condition is made worse because some parents cannot read and write and can only communicate in their mother tongue, making it difficult for them to assist their children with their homework.

The findings indicate that parents' participation in student learning can promote students' academic performance, and parental participation includes participating in school activities, supervising children's education, and communicating with teachers. It is believed that parental participation should be an all-around process that needs to be considered from various perspectives, such as school, family, and community (Hill et al., D., 2009).

Table 5

Level of parents' involvement in students learning according to the area of Decision-Making

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a parent ...		
1. I voice my opinions regarding the school and its development.	3.12	Moderate Level
2. I involve myself in the school's decision-making regarding curriculum and learning strategies, financial planning, or the recruitment of teachers and staff.	2.36	Low Level
3. I have an influence over what happens in my child's classroom, by providing suggestions regarding class activities.	3.84	High Level
4. I can contact the school committee to voice my inquiries regarding my child's progress.	4.44	High Level
5. I participate in class organization as an officer.	4.38	High Level
6. I involve myself in the formulation of rules and regulations of the school.	4.40	High Level
7. I involve myself in the decision making regarding students welfare.	3.60	High Level
Overall Mean	3.73	High Level

Table 5 indicates the data on the level of parental involvement in the student's learning in the area of decision-making. Respondents assessed an overall mean score was 3.73 and interpreted it as a "high level." Most parents are good at involving themselves in school decision-making for their children's welfare.

However, to conduct a thorough analysis in Table 5, the respondents perceived a highest mean score of 4.40 on item No. 6, which states, "I involve myself in the formulation of rules and regulations of the school" and is interpreted as "high level," while the lowest mean of 2.36 was on item No. 2 which states "I involve myself in the school's decision-making regarding curriculum and learning strategies, financial planning, or the recruitment of teachers and staff" and interpreted as "low level."

This implies that only some parents can involve themselves in making decisions regarding curriculum and learning strategies and other administrative concerns of the school.

The result is supported by the study of Mudzielwana (2015). The results showed that parents do not involve themselves and become reluctant to help their children do homework at home. Some parents state that they are not teachers – after all, they pay school fees, which helps supplement the government subsidy.

Table 6

Level of parents' involvement in students learning according to the area of Collaborating with the Community

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a parent ...		
1. I am involved in sharing ideas during parents conferences.	2.86	Moderate Level
2. I am attending my child community-based activities.	3.36	Moderate Level
3. I am involved in cooperative programs between the school and the local community, like programs for orphanage and elderly, local health clinics, local villages, etc.	3.40	Moderate Level
4. I am involved in the celebrations with the locals in the school area that are conducted by the school.	3.44	Moderate Level
5. I am involved in the clean-up drive in the community to promote environmental awareness.	3.50	High Level
6. I am collaborating with other parents in school projects.	2.78	Moderate Level
7. I am supporting the schools needs for my child's welfare.	3.54	High Level
Overall Mean	3.27	Moderate Level

Table 6 reveals the data on the level of parental involvement in the student's learning in the area of collaborating with the community. Respondents assessed an overall mean score was 3.27 and interpreted it as a "moderate level." This declares that most parents are somewhat good at collaborating with other parents and other locals in the school area for the welfare of the school at the same time, their children.

However, to conduct a deeper look analysis in Table 6, the respondents perceived a highest mean score of 3.54 on item No. 7, which states, "I am supporting the school needs for my child's welfare " and is interpreted as "high level," while the lowest mean of 2.78 was on item No. 6 which states "I am collaborating with other parents in school projects" and interpreted as "moderate level."

This implies that only some parents have taken the opportunity to collaborate with other parents regarding their children's schoolwork and assignments, for they need more time to have conversations and plan for some school projects. It will agree and support whatever the school needs a project that can significantly help their children's learning.

The result is supported by the study of Mudzielwana (2015). The results showed that parents do not involve themselves and become reluctant to help their children do their schoolwork at home. Some of the parent state that they are not teachers – after all, they pay school fees which helps to supplement the government subsidy.

Table 7

Comparative analysis in the level of parents' involvement in students learning in the area of Parenting when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Tounger	27	25.26	304.000	0.898		Not Significant
	Older	23	25.78				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	36	25.94	236.000	0.726	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	14	24.36				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	30	26.90	258.000	0.400		Not Significant
	Higher	20	23.40				

Table 7 presents the statistics on the significant differences in the level of parental involvement in the student's learning in the area of parenting when grouped and compared according to variables. The computed U is 304.00 with a *p*-value of 0.898, which is greater than the 0.05 significance level, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that "there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement to the student's learning in the area of parenting when grouped and compared according to age" is accepted.

On the variable highest educational attainment, the computed U is 236.000 with a *p*-value of 0.726, which is greater than the 0.05 level, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis states "there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in the student's learning in the area of parenting when grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment" is accepted.

Further, for variable average family monthly income, the computed U is 258.000 with a *p*-value of 0.400, which is greater than the 0.05 level, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis states "there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in the student's learning in the area of parenting when grouped and compared according to average family monthly income" is accepted.

This implies that the level of parental involvement in students' learning in parenting, when grouped and compared according to age, highest educational attainment, and average family monthly income, does not vary. Regardless of the variables mentioned, it does not influence the involvement of the parents in parenting toward the learning of their children.

The results concur with the study conducted by Manlangit et al. (2020), showing the interconnectedness of parents' educational levels. Educated parents earn more, can escape poverty, and benefit from a better quality of life. Furthermore, parents' educational attainment can heighten their feelings of competence and confidence in guiding their children's education. It manifests in different ways, such as being more proactive in checking their child's performance through parents-teachers association (PTA) meetings, providing their child's educational necessities, and other parental-educational duties.

Table 8

Comparative analysis in the level of parents' involvement in students learning in the area of Communicating when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Tounger	27	25.63	307.000	0.945		Not Significant
	Older	23	25.35				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	36	25.53	251.000	0.983	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	14	25.43				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	30	26.50	270.000	0.547		Not Significant
	Higher	20	24.00				

Table 8 presents the statistics on the significant differences in the level of parental involvement in the student’s learning in the area of communicating when grouped and compared according to variables. The computed U is 307.00 with a *p*-value of 0.945, which is greater than the 0.05 significance level, thus, interpreted as “not significant.” Therefore, the hypothesis that “there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement to the student’s learning in the area of communicating when grouped and compared according to age” is accepted.

On the variable highest educational attainment, the computed U is 251.000 with a *p*-value of 0.983, which is greater than the 0.05 level, thus, interpreted as “not significant.” Therefore, the hypothesis states “there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in the student’s learning in the area of communicating when grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment” is accepted.

Similarly, for variable average family monthly income, the computed U is 270.000 with a *p*-value of 0.547, which is greater than the 0.05 level, thus, interpreted as “not significant.” Therefore, the hypothesis states “there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in the student’s learning in the area of communicating when grouped and compared according to average family monthly income” is accepted.

This implies that the level of parental involvement in students’ communication learning, when grouped and compared according to age, highest educational attainment, and average family monthly income, does not vary. Regardless of the variables mentioned, it does not influence the parents' involvement in communicating with their children's learning.

Table 9

Comparative analysis in the level of parents’ involvement in students learning in the area of Decision-Making when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Tounger	27	25.59	308.000	0.960	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	23	25.39				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	36	27.42	183.000	0.127	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	14	20.57				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	30	24.53	271.000	0.557	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	20	26.95				

Table 9 presents the statistics on the significant differences in the level of parental involvement in the student’s learning in the area of decision-making when grouped and compared according to variables. The computed U is 308.00 with a *p*-value of 0.960, which is greater than the 0.05 significance level, thus, interpreted as “not significant.” Therefore, the hypothesis that states “there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement to the student’s learning in the area of decision-making when grouped and compared according to age” is accepted.

On the variable highest educational attainment, the computed U is 183.000 with a *p*-value of 0.127, which is greater than the 0.05 level, thus, interpreted as “not significant.” Therefore, the hypothesis states “there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in the student’s learning in the area of decision making when grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment” is accepted.

Similarly, for variable average family monthly income, the computed U is 271.000 with a *p*-value of 0.557, which is greater than the 0.05 level, thus, interpreted as “not significant.” Therefore, the hypothesis states “there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in the student’s learning in the area of decision-making when grouped and compared according to average family monthly income” is accepted.

This implies that the level of parental involvement in students’ learning in the area of decision-making, when grouped and compared according to age, highest educational attainment, and average family monthly income, does not vary. Regardless of the variables mentioned, it does not influence the involvement of the parents in decision-making regarding the school's academic concerns for the student’s welfare.

Table 10

Comparative analysis in the level of parents' involvement in students learning in the area of Collaborating with the Community when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Tounger	27	25.65	306.500	0.960		Not Significant
	Older	23	25.33				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	36	28.14	157.000	0.036	0.05	Significant
	Higher	14	18.71				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	30	24.57	272.000	0.571		Not Significant
	Higher	20	26.90				

Table 10 presents the statistics on the significant differences in the level of parental involvement in the student's learning in the area of collaborating with the community when grouped and compared according to variables. The computed U is 306.00 with a *p*-value of 0.960, which is greater than the 0.05 significance level, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis states "there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement to the student's learning in the area of collaborating with the community when grouped and compared according to age" is accepted.

On the variable highest educational attainment, the computed U is 157.000 with a *p*-value of 0.036, which is less than the 0.05 level, thus, interpreted as "significant." Therefore, the hypothesis states "there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in the student's learning in the area of collaborating with the community when grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment is "rejected."

Further, for variable average family monthly income, the computed U is 272.000 with a *p*-value of 0.571, which is greater than the 0.05 level, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis states "there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in the student's learning in the area of collaborating with the community when grouped and compared according to average family monthly income" is accepted.

This implies that the level of parental involvement in students' learning in collaborating with the community, when grouped and compared according to age and average family monthly income, does not vary. Regardless of the variables mentioned, it does not influence the involvement of the parents when it comes to collaborating with the community. Whereas when compared according to the highest educational attainment, the result varies. This is because parents with lower educational attainment dominated the findings. These are parents who are high school graduates. This indicates that these parents lack knowledge, exposure, and awareness of whom they must collaborate with regarding their children's welfare.

These findings conform with the studies conducted on the impact of family education investment and parents' education background on the academic performance of junior high school students, and through multiple regression analysis, it is concluded that family education investment and parents' education background have a significant positive impact on academic performance. In addition, this paper also explored the mediating role of family educational investment and parental educational experience on academic performance and found that family educational investment plays a mediating role between parental educational background and academic performance (Xiong et al., 2019).

Conclusions:

It is concluded that the younger parents contributed a more considerable number of respondents. Many of the parents have lower educational attainment, and many have a lower average family monthly income. It is also said that older parents with higher educational backgrounds would have better knowledge and understanding of involvement in developing their children's learning. It is concluded that many respondents are younger parents with low educational experiences and family incomes.

In the area of Parenting, most parents have less time to make or prepare reviewers for their examinations and test. Some parents are exhausted after doing household chores or office work. Hence, less time was allotted to their children. In comparison, some parents work during the day, so they need more time to prepare their reviewers. With a busy timetable, parents need more time to review their children's lessons as much as they would like.

In the area of Communicating, most parents rarely attend school conferences, specifically while giving report cards, because they sometimes feel that they are not welcome in schools aside from being preoccupied with many household chores and job demands.

In the area of Decision-making, only some parents can involve themselves in making decisions regarding curriculum and learning strategies and other administrative concerns of the school.

In Collaborating with the community, only some parents have taken the opportunity to collaborate with other parents regarding their children's schoolwork and assignments, for they need more time to have conversations and plan for some school projects. It will just agree and support whatever the school needs, a project that can significantly help their children's learning.

It is also concluded that regardless of parents' age and average family monthly income, they perform well in parenting, communicating, decision-making, and collaborating with the community to teach their children.

Further, parents' highest educational attainment is an intervening factor that may affect the involvement of the parents in facilitating students' learning.

Recommendations:

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations were advanced:

In the area of Parenting, it is recommended that teachers guide and assist parents in making a schedule for study and pointers on how to make a study guide for examinations. If possible, the scope of the lessons in every term must be given regularly to the parents during regular classroom PTA meetings to update the parents on their involvement in their student's learning. Parents can make a "To Do List" for a weekly schedule of review at home for their children so that they will be reminded all the time. Planner books can be a great help for students to plan for their study schedules before the examination.

In the area of Communicating, it is recommended that teachers create programs that will create a parent-teacher partnership, Recognition of parents for their involvement in school projects, and child's achievement in school aside from giving report cards. School heads and teachers should build a comfortable learning environment to sustain the learners' interest and open communication with the parents.

In the area of Decision-making, it is recommended that school heads and teachers may conduct regular consultations and orientation of the school vision and mission for the welfare of their children. Parents should be informed through letters or an info board with a schedule within the allotted time. With this, they will become interested and involved parents.

In the area of Collaborating with the community, Teachers and school heads can create a grouping for parents to collaborate on school projects with the goal of their children's welfare in school. The school can make an acquaintance party for the parents to strengthen their bonding with parents and teachers.

It is recommended to have aid in parental involvement; thus, educators in any school are encouraged to serve and implement extension programs akin to Parenting Education in a chosen community as a mission. The researchers also recommend that the programs designed for parent-teacher and parent-community interaction should be more emphasized to improve the parent-child relationship. It would benefit the parents, teachers, school, and community to have more input from each other's insights on improving parental involvement opportunities for all students.

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